

Supplementary Fig. 1 Western blot analyses of lysine methylation level and KDM2A in the CA1 at Sham rats treated with daminozide (10, 20, and 40 μM) for 24 h. GAPDH is used as loading control to normalize the relative levels of whole cellular KDM2A and lysine methylation. Data are expressed as percentage of value of Sham animals. $\&p < 0.05$ vs. Sham group with vehicle, injection intracerebroventricularly with isometric normal saline (for Methyl-K/ β -catenin, $p = 0.504$ at 10 μM , $p = 0.045$ at 20 μM , $p = 0.003$ at 40 μM , Kruskal-Wallis Test; for KDM2A, $p = 0.444$, One-Way ANOVA Test; $n = 6$ in each group).

SourceDataF#1A

SourceDataF#1B

SourceDataF#1C

SourceDataF#1E

SourceDataF#1F

SourceDataF#1G

SourceDataF#2C

SourceDataF#3C

SourceDataF#3E

SourceDataF#3F

SourceDataF#3G

SourceDataF#4A

SourceDataF#4B

SourceDataF#4D

SourceDataF#4C

SourceDataF#4E

SourceDataF#6D

SourceDataF#6E

SourceDataF#6F

SourceDataF#6G

SourceDataF#7C

SourceDataF#7D

SourceDataF#8F

SourceDataF#8G

SourceDataF#8H

